

Pramana and Naya in Jaina Logic

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[1] *Pramana* and *Naya* are two cardinal concepts in the Jaina theory of knowledge of what there is or what the Jainas say there is. It is almost impossible to say as to what the Jaina thinker is doing in the vast literature on the methodology of knowledge without our having a reasonably clear idea of his usage of the terms *Pramana* and *Naya*. But when one wants to seek clarity on the issue of distinguishing *Pramana* from *Naya* and the two from their related concept *syat* one feels simply baffled. At least, this is how I felt when I found myself confronted with the following statements of the Jaina position on the question whether *Naya* is or is not a *Pramana* and what after all is the connection, if any, between the two :

- (T1) The class of *Pramana* sentences includes the whole class of *Naya* sentences. Only when the word *syat* or *kathamcit* is prefixed to a *Naya* sentence that it acquires the logical status of a *Pramana*. (1)
- (T2) The *Naya* consists in the particular intention of the knower who, suspending his judgment about the other parts, takes notice of one particular aspect of an object which is known through the *Pramana* of the scriptures. (2)
- (T3) The *Naya* sentences are used to communicate knowledge, but they cannot be said to be either *Pramana* or *Apramana*. (3)

The above three theses T₁, T₂, and T₃, it seems to me, are quite different from one another. The thesis T₁ suggests that, unless a *Naya* sentence is prefixed by the word *syat* or *kathamcit*, the *naya* sentence will not qualify to be a *pramana-vakya*. The thesis T₂ treats a *naya* sentence as a claim to knowledge, that is, a *pramana*, and when it is conjoined to the thesis T₄.

- (T4) As *Pramana* adds to knowledge by removing ignorance, so does *Naya* adds to knowledge by removing ignorance. (4)

The obvious thing that strikes one's mind is that a *naya* sentence communicating as it does knowledge of only one aspect of anything must itself be a *pramana*. It is plain then that if you accept the thesis T₁ you just cannot subscribe to the thesis T₂ conjoined to the thesis T₄. And conversely also. Faced with the dilemma of choosing one or the other alternative you are offered the thesis T₃, *namely*, that a *naya* sentence cannot be said to be either *pramana* or *apramana*. Apparently, the Jaina thinker has a way out of this discomforting situation. He may point out that we have misunderstood his position altogether. Prefix the word *syat* or *kathamcit* to the *naya* sentence.

(A) A *naya* sentence is a *pramana*

and to

(B) A *naya* sentence is not a *pramana*

and you obtain three perfectly consistent sentences

(C) *Syat*, a *naya* sentence is a *pramanna*

And

(D) *Syat*, a *naya* sentence is not a *pramana*

Or

(E) *Syat*, a *naya* sentence is *pramana* as well as *apramana*.(5)

I do not think that this way of going about one's business in a discussion on the methodology of knowledge or the logic of evidence with which the Jaina thinker obviously is concerned will solve or help to solve the problem. My own feeling is that one feels cheated when a solution of this kind is presented to one who is seriously engaged in understanding what the Jaina thinker is really doing when he makes the two notions of *naya* and *pramana* as the core concepts of his theory of knowledge. I propose therefore to follow a different tack to explicate the distinction exploiting of course whatever the relevant texts there are that are available to me.

[2] Consider a few examples that the Jaina thinker (6) has given in order to illustrate his conception of the notion of *naya*, *pramana* and *syat*. To say that "*Sadeva*" or that "This object has existence as its only property" is to exemplify a *durnaya* sentence. Again, to say that "Sat" or "This object has existence" is to exemplify a *naya* sentence. Finally, to assert "*Syat Sat*" or that "this object has existence as one of its infinite properties" is to make a statement which properly belongs to the class of *pramana* sentences. These examples do throw some light on what the Jaina thinker had in mind

when he used the words *naya* and *pramana*. But, at the same time, these raise the question, *namely* ; If prefixing *syat* or *kathamcit* to any sentence make it a *pramana* sentence, then how are we going to reconcile this with the other position, *namely*, that while in a *naya* sentence one only aspect or property or relation of something is asserted to be known, while in a *pramana-vakya*, the whole of something is asserted to be known (7)? This question arises because the logical form and function of a *naya* sentence does in no way suggest that the sentence is used to communicate information about the object of knowledge as 'a whole, that is, about whatever aspects, properties, or relations that object may have either in itself or as it is related to the other objects. And, this is one condition which a *pramana vakya* is supposed to satisfy. It is possible that the way I have stated the condition which distinguishes a *pramana vakya* from a *naya vakya* makes it a very stringent requirement to be satisfied by a *pramana vakya*. And, hopefully, it is very likely that the Jaina thinkers never meant it is exactly the way as I have put it. However, in the rich philosophical literature which deals with the question of differentiating a *naya vakya* from a *pramana vakya*, they have tried to exploit the notion of *adesa* in outlining the features which are distinctive of a *naya vakya* but not of a *pramana vakya*, and also those which are distinctive of a *pramana vakya* but not of a *naya vakya*.

[3] The relevant Dictionary meaning of the word *adesa* is 'advice, instruction, precept, or rule'. But by an *adesa*, the Jaina thinker means a 'point of view'. We can look upon some particular thing from different points of view. Observing an object from one and only one point of view to the exclusion of every other, according to the Jaina thinker, does not enable us to describe an object as, adequately as one may wish it to be described. It is a different thing altogether that we may be interested in knowing and describing only one aspect or property of the object. But, knowing and describing only one property of the object does not mean knowing and describing its other properties also. This idea of differentiating a *specific description* of only one property from a *general description* of an object of knowledge is of the fundamental importance to the Jaina thinker. He employs this idea to divide (8) all *adesa* sentences into two sub-types : First *sakaladesa* sentences and secondly, *vikaladesa* sentences. A *vikaladesa* (9) sentence is used to describe one and only one *dharma* or property of *sat* or what is real, while a *sakaladesa* (10) sentence is used to give a general description of *sat* or what is real. To put it differently, a *sakaladesa* sentence describes what is *real synthetically*; it communicates information

about the entire, undivided reality, while a *vikaladesa* sentence describes the various *dharmas* or properties of ‘*sat*’ *analytically* it communicates information about an ‘*amsa*’, an aspect or a part of what is real. This is how the Jaina thinker differentiates a *sakaladesa vakya* from a *vikaladesa vakya*. This distinction, however, is expressed in the traditionalistic jargon; but it may be stated in the ordinary language as the distinction between a *specific description* and a *general description* of what is real. A *sakaladesa* sentence is used to give a general description; while a sentence is employed to give a specific description of what is real. Both the types of sentences, however, are used to describe what the Jaina thinker calls ‘*sat*’ (11) or reality. And, it seems to me that differentiating these two types of description sentences is a perfectly legitimate thing to do for purposes of describing reality. But unfortunately, the distinction cannot be exploited to explicate the logical difference between a *Pramana vakya* and a *naya vakya*. Logically, both a *sakaladesa* sentence and also a *vikaladesa* sentences are bearer of true (of course, contingently true) information. Whether the information communicated by means of them in true or false is something which depends entirely upon what *pramana* is adduced in support of them. If the sentences are well-supported by one or more *pramana* they are said to be true, and if they are ill-supported, they are said to be false. The Jaina assertion (12) that a *sakaladesa vakya* is a *pramana vakya* while a *vikaladesa vakya* is a *naya vakya* is simply untenable. Differentiating a *pramana vakya* from a *naya vakya* on the basis merely of the extent or quantum of information they are used to communicate, will not do. We need a different criterion for distinguishing a *pramana vakya* from a *naya vakya* from the criterion on the basis of which we differentiate a *sakaladesa vakya* from a *vikaladesa vakya*. The Jaina thinker, it seems to me, has failed to see that the distinction between the first type of sentences necessarily requires the notion of truth or confirmation, while the distinction between the second type of sentences really does not. And if he uses the same criterion of division in both the cases, the Jaina logician could then be accused of having committed what in the traditional logic is known as the fallacy of cross division.

[4] Now, consider an example of a *vikaladesa* sentence :

(F) This object has existence.

Consider also an example of a *naya vakya*:

(G) This object has existence.

If you look at (F) and (G), both are identical sentences; and logically also they have the same status. The Jaina thinker, however, classifies them differently.

Why he does this, is not at all clear. It is not clear at least to me. He may have very good reasons for doing this; but no where, so far as I know, does he state or even suggest what reasons he has to characterize them differently. At the same time, he would not identify them as the same sentences. If he did this he will have to say that, as *a naya vakya* when prefixed by the word *syat* or *kathamcit* becomes a *pramana vakya* (13) so in the same manner *a yikaladesa vakya* when prefixed by the word *syat* or *kathamcit* would acquire the status of *a sakaladesa* sentence. But, I do not think that this consequence is acceptable to the Jaina thinker. This can be shown as follows. Consider an example of *a sakaladesa vakya*

(H) This object has infinite properties.

This sentence satisfies the condition of *a sakaladesa* sentence.

Prefix now the word *syat* or *kathamcit* to the *vikaladesa* sentence an example of which is The sentence (F) above, and the resulting sentence would be

(I.) This object has the property of existence as one of its infinite properties.

The two sentences (H) and (I) are in no way logically equivalent; nor are they semantically equivalent. Besides, the sentence (I) gives more information than the information given by the sentence (H). It follows that even if the prefixing of the word *syat* or *kathamcit* to a *naya* sentence turns it into *a pramana vakya*, the same device does not turn *a vikaladega* sentences into *a sakaladega vakya*. The point of the argument is that the criterion of distinguishing *a pramana vakya* from *a naya vakya* must be different from the criterion of differentiating a *sakaladesa vakya* from a *vikaladesa vakya*.

[5] On my analysis, the distinction between *a sakaladesa* sentence and a *vikaladesa* sentence is a distinction with respect to the quantum or the extent of information communicated by means of these sentences. A *vikaladesa* sentence is a specific description of some specific aspect of what is real, while, *sakaladesa* sentence is a general description of what is real. No question whatever of their truth values is involved in so far as we are concerned with a criterion of distinguishing them from each other. The distinction between *a pramana vakya* and *a naya vakya*, on the other hand, involves a criterion which has to do with the truth values of these sentences. And here also my feeling is that the innocent device of prefixing the word *syat* or *kathamcit* to a *naya* sentence will not turn it into *a pramana* sentence. Or, for that matter, removing the prefix *syat* or *kathamcit* from a *pramana* sentence will not turn it into *a naya* sentence. This can be shown as follows –

The notion of *naya* is tethered to the ways in which *Sat* may be described (14) If we make a distinction between *dravya* and *pariyaya* a distinction frequently made by the Jaina thinker, then *Sat* may be described either according to the *dravyarthika naya* or according to the *pariyayarthika naya* (15), in other words, either by emphasizing on the *pariyayas* or properties which an object has, or by emphasizing on the *dravya* or substance of which the predicates are asserted to be true or false (16). The result, however, will be a description of what is real or *Sat*. Giving a description of *Sat* is not saying that the given description is true or false. To show its truth or falsity you have to offer one or more relevant *pramanas* or evidences in confirmation of your description of *sat*. It is in this way that the notion of *pramana* is related to the notion of *naya*. Unless *pramana vakyas* are adduced in support of a *naya vakya*, the *naya vakyas* remain what they are, neither confirmed nor disconfirmed descriptions. Merely prefixing the word *syat* or *kathamcit* does not transform them into *pramana vakyas*. Particularly, under the circumstance that a Jaina statement is a privileged statement in that the word *syat* or *kathamcit* is always prefixed to it either explicitly or contextually or it is just tacitly understood to have been prefixed (17). Consider, for instance, the sentence.

(J) *Sat is anekantika.* (18)

This sentence (J) is a *pramana vakya*. The word *syat* or *kathamcit* is apparently not prefixed to it. Unless the word is tacitly assumed to have been prefixed to it, the sentence (J). does not qualify to be a *pramana vakya*. Then, how is it that it occurs as such without the prefix *syat* or *kathamcit* as a *pramana vakya* in the Jaina literature ? Our answer is: Not that the word *syat* or *kathamcit* when prefixed to it transforms in into a true statement ; but it is really the *pramana* or the evidence or the argument (19) that is adduced in favour of it that it makes it a true or an acceptable statement. The point of the argument is that it is the *pramarja* alone which transforms a sentence like (J) above into a *pramana vakya* ; the prefixing of the word *syat* or *kathamcit* does not do this ; the sentence remains where it is, a mere description only or a *naya vakya*.

[6] What I have done in this short paper is briefly this : I have argued for the thesis that a *vikaladesa* sentence and a *sakaladesa* sentence logically stand on a different footing from a *pramana* sentence and a *naya* sentence, and that the criterion of differentiating the first pair of sentences is different from the criterion of distinguishing the second pair of sentences. I have held the thesis that the question of How to describe that is real is conceptually different from the question of How to decide the truth values of sentences which are used to describe what is real. I have maintained the view that a *naya* sentence

whether the word *syat* or *kathamcit* (20) is prefixed to it or not, is a sentence which belongs to the set of those sentences that are offered in answer to the first question, namely, How to describe what is real: while *pramana vakyas* with or without the prefix *syat* or *kathamcit* are evaluated true or confirmed descriptions of what is said to be real.

Notes and References

1. Mallisena's *Syadvadamanjari* with Hemacandra's *Anyayoga-Vyavaccheda-Dvatritsika* (Bombay Sanskrit and Prakrit Series No. LXXXII ; 1933) p. 167.
2. Vadideva Suri's *Pramana-Naya-Tattvalokalamkara* (Jain Sahitya Vikas Mandal, Bombay; 1967). p. 508.
3. Yasovijaya Gani's *Jainatarkabhasa* (Delhi, 1973). p. 21 : Cf. *Tattvartha-slokavarttika*, 1.6.21.5.
4. *Pramana-Naya-Tattvalokalamkara* p. 538.
5. *Jain-Tarka-Bhasa* ; p. 21.
6. *Syadvadamanjari* ; pp. 159-169.
7. *Pramana-Naya-Tattvalokalamkara* ; p. 508.
8. *Anyayoga-Vyavaccheda-Dvatritsika* ; St. 23 ; p. 139 of *Syadvadamanjari*, op. cit.
9. *Syadvadamanjari*, p. 145. Cf. *Ratnakaravatarika*, Chapter 4.
10. Ibid, p. 146.
11. *Anyayoga-Vyavaccheda-Dvatritsika* ; St. 21 ; p. 133-34 of *Syadvadamanjari*. Cf. *Tattvarthaslokavarttika* ; V. 29.
12. *Syadvadamanjari*, pp. 145-46.
13. *Syadvadamanjari*, p. 167.
14. Ibid, p. 161.
15. Ibid, pp. 138-48. Also, *Jain-Tarka-Bhasa*, p. 21.
16. Ibid, pp. 138-48.
17. Ibid, p. 245.
18. Ibid, p. 136.
19. Ibid, p. 137.
20. In this paper, I have not discussed the logic of *Syat vakyas*. That forms the subject of another paper.